

THEORIZATION OF THE POSSIBILITY OF OBSERVING AND MEASURING THE ELECTROMAGNETIC FIELD OF A NEURON

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Abstract - This study analyzes the electromagnetic field generated by neurons during electrical and chemical communication. It utilizes Ohm's Law and biological data to determine the fundamental elements of the magnetic field, such as the current generated by the action potential, the resulting magnetic field, and membrane capacitance. Additionally, a graph was created in Scilab to visualize the electrical behavior of a neuron.

Keywords: Electromagnetic Field; Neuronal Communication; Action Potential; Graphical Visualization (Scilab).

INTRODUCTION

The inspiration for the research behind this article originated from an established law in physics, Ampère's Law, proposed by French physicist André-Marie Ampère in 1826 [10], which states that an electric current flowing through a conductor generates a magnetic field around it. In other words, any electric current produces a magnetic field in its vicinity. Additionally, the Ampère-Maxwell Law, formulated by James Clerk Maxwell in 1865 [11], extends Ampère's Law by including the concept that not only electric currents can generate magnetic fields, but also variations in electric fields. Broadly, it asserts that any circuit with electric current or a variable electric field generates an electromagnetic field.

Moreover, knowledge of neurons, particularly the structures of this cell as studied by Camillo Golgi (1843-1926) [1] and Santiago Ramón y Cajal (1852-1934) [2], as well as the concept of chemical synapse proposed by Charles Sherrington (1857-1952) [3] and validated by Otto Loewi (1873-1961) [4], along with electrical communication elucidated by Nobel laureates in 1963, Alan Hodgkin and Andrew Huxley [6], [7], and the integration between electrical and chemical transmission proposed by John Eccles (1903-1997) [5], [8], provided a solid foundation for this research.

These insights allowed for a connection between these two fields of knowledge, which, though distinct, share a common element: the electric current in neural communication that triggers bodily responses, such as the movement of an arm. This article thus aims to measure the electromagnetic field, identify the main aspects involved, and highlight the challenges encountered.

DEVELOPMENT

The research initially encountered several challenges, such as interpreting the duality between electrical communication (action potential) and chemical communication (neurotransmitter release at synapses) for graphical representation. This included the difficulty of correctly interpreting known values and, ultimately, how this communication could be measured accurately.

To establish a clear line of understanding, we must divide the problem into parts. The first issue to address is the aforementioned duality, essential for building the theoretical foundation of the research. This duality is significant due to the distinct

differences between the types of signals involved: the action potential, which is electrical, and the neurotransmitter transmission, which is chemical. When analyzing the electrical signals of a neuron on an oscilloscope, for example, we can observe a "dead zone," or period of electrical inactivity, which is significantly longer than the interval between the initial recorded electrical signals.

This distinction between the periods of activity and inactivity of the neuron, as well as the variation in signals, is crucial for interpreting the data and creating graphs that represent both types of communication clearly and precisely. Moreover, understanding how these two forms of transmission interact can enhance measurement accuracy and facilitate the development of models that accurately represent bioelectrical and biochemical processes.

With this established, we can proceed to the second point, which is interpreting the known data. Among these data, studied in biology, are the electric charges present in a neuron and their measurements, along with the duration of bioelectrical and biochemical processes. To construct a graph, we need to use what was established in the first issue, where we can interpret the electrical communication values as peak-to-peak. This is because the conduction of the electrical signal along the axon, through action potentials, shows high-frequency peaks visible on an oscilloscope. In other words, the electrical variations along the cell, caused by electrical information, serve to generate responses such as muscle contraction, making the graph more intuitive.

Meanwhile, chemical communication can be represented as a time interval, as the neurotransmitter transmission process at synapses is slower. Thus, chemical communication can be expressed as the time interval between consecutive peaks (action potentials). Although simplified, this approach provides an intuitive idea of how the two forms of communication relate to the oscillatory behavior of neurons.

With this foundation, we can proceed with utilizing the data on the charges present in the cells to construct a graph representing electrical signals in the bioelectric context. For this, we use the following values:

- Resting Potential: The voltage measured across the plasma membrane of a neuron in an inactive state (not sending signals), whose typical value is about -70 mV [18], [19], [20].

- **Action Potential:** When the neuron is stimulated and reaches a voltage threshold (usually between -55 mV and -50 mV), it enters the action potential phase, where the membrane potential rapidly becomes positive, reaching a peak of +30 mV to +40 mV [18], [19], [20].
- **Hyperpolarization:** After the peak of the action potential, sodium channels close and potassium channels open, allowing K^+ to exit the cell. This restores the resting potential, but the membrane often hyperpolarizes, becoming more negative than the resting state, reaching -80 mV or -90 mV before returning to the resting level of -70 mV [18], [19], [20].

With this, we can obtain the graph in Fig. 1, in which we observe that the blue lines show the action potentials, representing the electrical communication in neurons, which occur at regular intervals. The dashed red lines represent the intervals between the peaks, indicating the moments when chemical communication occurs at the synapses. During these periods, there is no perceptible electrical activity in the postsynaptic neuron while neurotransmitters are being released and received. With the creation of Fig. 1, we can use it to assist in the calculation of the electromagnetic field, as the peaks and fluctuations in potential allow us to understand the electric current associated with the action potentials. This current is essential for calculating the electromagnetic field generated by the neuron, using laws such as Ampère's, for example.

Fig. 1 – Graph generated by Scilab

To construct the graph shown in Fig. 1 in Scilab, we need to create a time vector from 0 to 100 ms (milliseconds) and generate 1000 equally spaced values using the `linspace` function, as shown in Fig. 2.

```
t = linspace(0, 100, 1000);
```

Fig. 2 – Definition of Time in Scilab

With the definition of time, we should use the modulated sine function to generate action potentials, conditioning these peaks to occur at specific time intervals. Thus, we apply a condition where $\sin(t \times 0.1)$ is greater than 0.9. The reason for using this logical condition is that whenever the function returns 1 (true), it activates the "activation

window" for the action potentials; otherwise, it returns 0 (false), meaning that the action potential is not generated. In this way, activation is created at specific moments, mimicking electrical activity.

When creating this "activation window," we use $\sin(t \times 0.5)$, which generates a sine function that smoothly fluctuates over time. Once these two important points are established for generating the electrical communication graph, we need to use the operator `.*`, which performs element-wise multiplication between vectors. Additionally, we use `*100` to amplify the magnitude of the peaks to 100 mV, a typical value for a neuronal action potential, as shown in Fig. 3.

```
action_potential = sin(t * 0.5) .* (sin(t * 0.1) > 0.9) * 100;
```

Fig. 3 – Creation of Action Potentials

With the creation of the code line for the electric communication graph, we now need to create the chemical communication part, keeping in mind that this process is slower and occurs between action potentials, i.e., during the intervals when there is no electrical activity. To do this, we use the function `zeros(t)`, which creates a vector of the same size as `t`, filled with zeros, representing the absence of electrical activity during chemical communication.

Next, we create a logical condition similar to that of electrical communication by using `find(sin(t * 0.1) <= 0.9)`. This function locates the points where $\sin(t \times 0.1)$ is less than or equal to 0.9, meaning outside the moments when an electrical peak occurs.

During these intervals of electrical inactivity, we will assign the value of -10 mV to chemical communication, representing the potential difference at the moments when neurotransmitters are being released. This is done by setting the value to -10, as illustrated in Fig. 4.

```
chemical_spacing = zeros(t);  
chemical_spacing(find(sin(t * 0.1) <= 0.9)) = -10;
```

Fig. 4 – Creation of Chemical Spacings

With the definitions of electrical and chemical communications established, it will be necessary to plot the graphs separately so that we can better observe the behaviors of the two neuronal communications. For plotting the action potentials (electrical communication), we will use the command `plot(t, action_potential, 'b')`, where 'b' represents the blue color. For plotting the intervals between peaks (chemical communication), we will use `plot(t, chemical_spacing, 'r--')`, where 'r--' corresponds to a dashed red line, as shown in Fig. 5.

```
plot(t, action_potential, 'b', t, chemical_spacing, 'r--');
```

Fig. 5 – Plotting of the Graphs

To organize the information in the graph, we will use the command `xtitle`, which defines the title of the graph and the labels for the axes. The title will be set as "Graphical Representation of Neuronal Communication (Electrical and Chemical)," and for the x and y axes, the labels will be "Time (ms)" and "Potential (mV)." To add a legend for the two data sets in the graph, the legend command will be used, with the labels "Electrical Communication (Action

Potentials)" and "Chemical Communication (Spacing)." Finally, we will use the function xgrid(1) to add a grid to the graph, making it easier to visualize.

Using Fig. 1, we can proceed to construct the calculation, in which Ohm's Law will be applied, as shown in Fig. 6, to calculate the level of current generated in the cell. We know that the action potential reaches peaks of approximately 30 mV to 40 mV, and the resting potential is around -70 mV. However, to perform the calculation, it is necessary to have the value of the resistance of the neuron's membrane, which is generally Around $10^6 \Omega$ (1 megaohm) [12], [13].

$$I = \frac{V}{R}$$

Fig. 6 – Ohm's Law Formula

Thus, we can apply the already known values, using the action potential as the value of the electric potential (V), as this is the moment when the neuron exhibits the highest electrical activity, and the resistance of the neuron's membrane as the electrical resistance (R). Consequently, we conclude that the current generated by the action potential is 40 nA (40 nanoamperes), as shown in Fig. 7.

$$I = \frac{40 \times 10^{-3}}{10^6} = 40 \text{ nA}$$

Fig. 7- Aplicação dos valores na fórmula da Lei de Ohms

Now, with the discovery of the current value present during the action potential period, we can proceed to calculate the Magnetic Field, for which we will use the Biot-Savart Law shown in Fig. 8. It will be necessary to use the vacuum permeability constant, which is $4\pi \times 10^{-7} T \cdot m/A$, the current of 40 nA, the length of the axon segment given as $10^{-5} m$ [14], [15], and lastly, the distance from the observation point, which is also given as $10^{-5} m$ since it is in the axon, which will be the point of interest for the calculation.

$$B = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \cdot \frac{I \cdot dl}{r^2}$$

Fig. 8 - Formula of Biot-Savart Law

Thus, using the vacuum permeability constant, known as the magnetic permeability of free space (μ_0), the electric current shown in Fig. 7, the length of the axon as the length of the small conductor element generating the field (dl), and finally, the distance from the observation point as the distance between the current element and the point where the field is being calculated (r), we conclude that the magnetic field generated by a neuron is approximately 10 pT (picotesla), as shown in Fig. 8.

$$B = \frac{4\pi \times 10^{-7}}{4\pi} \cdot \frac{40 \times 10^{-9} \cdot 10^{-5}}{(10^{-5})^2} = 40 \times 10^{-11} T$$

Fig. 8 – Application of the values in the Biot-Savart Law formula

Before we conclude the calculations, we need to calculate the energy stored in the membrane, which is essential because the plasma membrane acts as a capacitor, and this energy is crucial for the transmission of electrical signals in the neuron, particularly during the action potential.

To calculate this, we need the membrane capacitance C_m , which is known to be approximately $1 \mu F/cm^2$ (microfarad per square centimeter) [16], [17], and we will use 40 nA (40 nanoamperes) as the electric potential difference across the membrane (V). We can estimate the energy stored in the membrane during the action potential using the formula shown in Fig. 9.

$$E = \frac{1}{2} C_m V^2$$

Fig. 9 – Formula for capacitance and storage of electrical energy.

By applying the values, we arrive at a value of 8 nJ (nanojoules), as shown in Fig. 10. Thus, with all the values we have already calculated, we found that the current generated by the neuron's action potential is 40 nA, the magnetic field generated by the current is 40 pT, and the energy stored in the neural membrane during the action potential is $8 \times 10^{-10} J$, which can also be expressed as 0.8 nJ.

$$E = \frac{1}{2} \times 1 \times 10^{-6} \cdot (40 \times 10^{-3})^2 = 8 \times 10^{-10} J$$

Fig. 10 – Application of values in the capacitance formula.

These calculations provide a basic idea of how electrical signals in neurons can generate electromagnetic fields and how these signals can be measured and interpreted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Using the data obtained from the calculations, it is possible to observe that, when analyzing the electromagnetic field generated by a neuron that produces a current of 40 nA, a magnetic field of 40 pT, and an action potential with energy of 0.8 nJ, we can understand various aspects of the electromagnetic field generated by neurons:

- Current of 40 nA: The current of 40 nA represents the flow of ions (electric charges) across the neuron's membrane during the action potential. This flow is responsible for electrical communication in the nervous system. The current is directly related to the amplitude and speed of propagation of the electrical signal.
- Magnetic field of 40 pT: According to the Biot-Savart Law, an electric current generates a magnetic field of approximately 40 pT. This magnetic field is weak but can be measured with sensitive equipment, such as high-precision magnetometers.

Biologically, the magnetic field generated by neurons is not strong enough to have a significant magnetic impact outside the brain, but it can influence the dynamics of currents at the cellular level.

- Action potential of 0.8 nJ: The energy of 0.8 nJ associated with the action potential reflects the energy stored and released during the activation of a neuron. This energy is used to transmit the electrical signal along the axon and, subsequently, to trigger the release of neurotransmitters at the synapses.

With this, we can interpret generally that the electromagnetic field generated by a neuron is the result of the interaction between the electric current and the magnetic field associated with the action potential. Although the generated magnetic field is small, it is part of the set of electromagnetic effects that govern the propagation of electrical signals in the brain. The electric field, on the other hand, is related to changes in membrane potential, while the magnetic field depends on the current flowing during these events.

These characteristics show that although the magnetic field of a single neuron is weak, the sum of many neurons that are simultaneously active can create signals that can be detected at larger levels, such as those appearing in tests like EEG (electroencephalography) or MEG (magnetoencephalography). However, it is worth noting that despite having fixed values already known in the field of neuroscience, the electromagnetic behavior can be more variable; that is, depending on the circumstances, such as emotions, for example, neurons can exhibit highly varied electrical behaviors, generating new magnetic fields, new currents, and capacitance.

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